

Training School Teachers to Use Robots as an Educational Tool: the Impact on Robotics Perception

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Abstract. This study investigates whether an educational robotics training program for kindergarten, primary, and secondary teachers causes them to change their impressions of a robotic platform. Questionnaires submitted before and after a 3-month training program were used to assess the opinions of 40 teachers. The training program aided in bringing teachers' expectations closer to the actual potential of the robot. The course seems to level participants' impressions: differences between STEM and literary teachers before the program are no longer detected after it. Although those with a wider technological background have more willingness to use the robot, all the teachers, in the end, perceived the robotic platform as appreciated and beneficial for the education of students. Our findings highlight the crucial benefit of a training program in robotics for teachers: it not only provides the knowledge to use a robotic platform but also helps form a more informed vision of the possibilities afforded by robotics platforms for education.

Keywords: Robots in Education · Technology at School · Robotics acceptance

1 Introduction

The use of social robots is growing in the educational field, especially for children, to enhance and support their learning. In this context, robots can positively

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affect both cognitive and affective aspects [1]. Most studies concerning robots in education focus on students, even if they are not the only stakeholders involved. Teachers represent a relevant portion of users of educational robotics. They are experts in designing and evaluating pupils' learning; therefore, assessing their opinions, expectations, and concerns about robots in education may be crucial to improving the modalities of use of robots at school.

In the last decades, researchers started investigating teachers' impressions of educational robots using surveys. In the works of Kim et al. [16] and Reich et al. [20], teachers reported negative attitudes about teaching and learning with educational robots; in Lee et al. [17], they also demonstrated to be more critical about integrating robots into schools than students and parents. However, teachers with greater technology commitment reported more positive attitudes towards educational robots [20]. A similar result was evidenced in a survey administered to elementary school teachers after a robotics workshop, in which the intention of use of the robot in educational activities positively correlated with the teachers' attitude to technology, other than with the perceived usefulness of the robot [9]. Interestingly, elementary school teachers seem to have more negative attitudes and less eagerness to use educational robots than their middle-school colleagues [20]; they appear apprehensive about the impact of robots on younger school children's social skills that might suffer from the use of artificial agents. Similar concerns were expressed in focus groups analyzed by Serholt et al. [22], where teachers were worried that robots not able to interact on the same emotional plan as humans might lead children to develop impaired emotional intelligence. Besides, they feared that children might become over-reliant on robots and lose the capacity to be critical. Additionally, in both [20] and [21], teachers believed that the limited access to the robots could cause competitiveness among students and had the impression that pupils would quickly lose their interest in the robots. In the same works, other teachers' concerns regarded the extra workload that robots would bring to them and the possibility of robots taking their place in the future. Thanks also to science fiction literature and filmography (e.g., Blade Runner [6], Terminator [2]), the idea that robots will soon replace humans in their jobs is widespread in the collective naive imagination. People without experience in robotics are often exposed to the concept of a robot as a threat. Experts in robotics know that it is most likely not the case: in the following years, in social settings, robots will probably be used just as tools or simple helpers and will not be completely autonomous. To fill the gap between naive imagination and reality, we believe that users - teachers in our case - could benefit from learning first-hand the functioning of these robotics devices to understand their potential and limits fully. In this way, they can integrate them effectively into the learning programs. Despite all their concerns, in [22], even teachers themselves emphasized the need for adequate training so that they could comprehend a robot's functioning.

The above-reported works represent suitable indicators of teachers' opinions on educational robots, even if they do not include robotics activity in authentic learning contexts. Incorporating HRI in real-world learning scenarios represents a

promising chance to gain a more comprehensive overview of educational robotics, but only a few studies consider teachers' points of view. Among those, Westlund et al. [25] carried out a two-month study in a kindergarten in which children interacted with a Tega robot. They administered pre and post-questionnaires to the teachers who supervised the activity. From before to after the study, their enthusiasm for employing a social robot in their classrooms declined together with their belief that the Tega robot would benefit students' education. They also would have used it differently than how proposed by the researchers. This finding suggests once again that educators may benefit from learning robotics skills to make the device behave as they deem appropriate.

The previous studies highlight a need to provide robotics training programs for teachers to promote the deployment of educational robotics in schools. At the same time, it would be necessary to understand whether and how a training program affects the perception of robotics of teachers with different backgrounds and in different school types. To this aim, in this work, we questioned teachers before and after a robotics training program that included theoretical and practical aspects of using the NAO robot.

2 Research Questions

We formulated three research questions by drawing inspiration from previous work related to teachers' opinions about robots in education. Considering that, in the media, robots are mostly portrayed as autonomous, error-proof machines endowed with self-consciousness, we expect teachers to project these expectations on NAO at the beginning of the training program; we assume that the training would help them to be aware of the real potential of the robot. Thus we asked:

RQ1: Will the training program aid in lowering teachers' naive expectations of robots' skills and thus help them become aware of the true potential of the robot? Will this positively or negatively affect the intentions of using the device?

RQ2: Are teachers' age, previous knowledge about technology, the subject taught (STEM or literary), and the type of school they teach in (kindergarten, primary, secondary) correlated with their impression of NAO and their will to use it in class?

RQ3: At the end of the training program, how will teachers evaluate the enjoyment and participation of the class in the robotics activities? Will they find these activities useful for the education of their students?

3 Robotics training program

The NaoToKnow project was funded under a call for proposals of the Italian Ministry of Education and implemented by the national network of educational institutes ARETE+4NAO¹. The project involves twenty-three schools in Italy

¹ <https://www.icmamelipalestrina.edu.it/arete4nao/>

engaged in training their teachers on the topics of educational robotics and advanced coding, with the aim of the implementation of inclusive educational activities through the use of humanoid robotics and innovative teaching methodologies within sample classes. The educational training was delivered by Scuola di Robotica² and the primary objective was to provide the necessary skills for teachers to introduce humanoid robotics within curricular lessons and laboratory activities. The training involved 106 teachers from kindergarten, primary and secondary schools. The course lasted three months and involved teachers participating in thirty hours of online training dedicated to developing skills for the use of humanoid robotics in the classroom. Every school owned a NAO robot at the teachers' disposal to perform the practical activities proposed in the course. First of all, teachers were familiarized with programming using Open Roberta³, an online simulator for programming the NAO; then, the training included the fundamentals of how to program the robot NAO on Choregraphe⁴ through block programming (a visual and intuitive programming method). Specifically, the course included the following teachings:

1. Introduction to humanoid robotics;
2. Introduction and familiarization with NAO;
3. How to connect NAO to a router;
4. Building dialogues, using blocks set up on Choregraphe and programming in Python;
5. How to make NAO walk;
6. Creating personalized movements, using the Timeline on Choregraphe;
7. Creating a synchronized movement with Coregraphe;
8. Face and object recognition, using NAO's camera;
9. Programming NAO's touch sensors;
10. How to acquire data with NAO's sensors.

At the end of the program, teachers participating in the course built a final project with their students: each class made a short video presentation of the activities completed during the training and prepared a live demonstration of them using NAO. The projects were presented at a final in-person event, where Scuola di Robotica's instructors revised them: all the projects were evaluated positively.

During the training course, the teachers had the possibility to participate in a research project coordinated by Scuola di Robotica, the University of Genoa, and the Italian Institute of Technology, focused on understanding students' and teachers' robot perception, by replying to a series of questionnaires at the beginning and at the end of the course.

² <https://www.scuoladirobotica.it/>

³ <https://lab.open-roberta.org/>

⁴ <https://www.softbankrobotics.com/emea/en/support/nao-6/downloads-softwares>

4 Methods

4.1 Participants

Participants were recruited from the 106 teachers that joined the NAO To Know project. The study was approved by the University of Genoa’s ethical committee (n. 20220317, 03/17/2022). Teachers signed an informed consent form and completed two sets of questionnaires: one after the first lesson of the project and another after the last one. The first set of questionnaires (Q1) was fully completed by 71 teachers, while 52 participants fully completed the second one (Q2). For both Q1 and Q2, 12 participants were excluded from further analysis because they failed to answer correctly to the attention-bump item (i.e., “to demonstrate your attention, answer 5 to this question”) that was inserted in the survey to prevent random responses. In the questionnaires, teachers were asked to insert a personal anonymous code, self-created according to our indications, to connect the two questionnaire answers. 40 participants fully completed both questionnaires ($n_1 = 40$, 7 males, 33 females; age: $M = 47.9$, $SD = 8.13$); 10% of the sample comprises teachers from kindergarten, 37.5% of primary school teachers, and the remaining 52.5% of secondary school teachers.

4.2 Questionnaires

The questionnaires were administered in Italian, using Survey Monkey⁵ and required about 15 minutes to be completed. The surveys were created ad hoc using items previously utilized in HRI and educational contexts to assess the teachers’ impression of the robot NAO. Q1 consisted in:

- Twelve items to assess *Agency and Patience* i.e., the attributed capacity to act and to feel, and six items of *Mind Attribution* i.e., the tendency to attribute a mind to other agents, from Gray et al.[12] (e.g., "I believe the robot NAO is able to feel pain"; "...to act morally"; "...to think").
- Nine items from the scale *Warmth and Competence* i.e., the attribution of being heartfelt and intelligent to an agent, by Fiske et al. [8] (e.g., "I believe the robot Nao is independent"; "...sincere").
- Six items from *Human-like appearance* scale i.e., the level of physical similarity with the humans, by Ferrari et al. [7] (e.g., "In my opinion NAO looks like a human").
- Three items from a short version of scale by Spaccatini et al. [23] to assess the *Likeability* i.e., the degree of liking the NAO (e.g., "I think NAO is nice").
- *UTAUT Unified Theory Of Acceptance And Use Of Technology* scale, already used for NAO by Vega et al. [24]. The scale is composed of the following sub-scale: *Intention of Use* (three items, e.g., "I think I will use NAO during classes"); *Perceived Enjoyment* (six items, e.g., "I like to do stuff with NAO"); *Perceived Sociability* (three items, e.g., "I believe the robot understands me"); *Trust* (two items, e.g., "I would follow the robot’s advice");

⁵ <https://it.surveymonkey.com>

Performance Expectancy (four items, e.g., "NAO's technology is useful for education in general"); *Effort Expectancy* (two items, e.g., "NAO's technology is easy to use").

Moreover, teachers answered the following ad hoc created items: "How familiar are you with educational robotics?"; "How familiar are you with technology at school?". To assess their confidence level in technology and robotics, they had to choose one of these options: "Very much"(5) "Much"(4), "Enough"(3), "A few"(2), or "At all"(1). Participants evaluated all items on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = "I strongly disagree", 5 = "I strongly agree"). Finally, demographic information (age, gender, education), including details about their job (school, type of subject taught), were collected. In Q2, the same scales administrated in Q1 were used, with the addition of the following scales:

- Three items from *Class Enjoyment scale* by D'Amico et al. [5] (e.g., "Activities with NAO have been funny for the class").
- Items from *Performance Expectancy* scale by Moore and Benbasat [19], composed of the two following sub-scales: *Ease of Use* (six items, "using NAO makes my work easier"); *Public Image* i.e. image in school derived from using the robot (4 items, e.g., "The fact that I used NAO improved my image at school").

4.3 Statistical Analyses

The statistical analyses were realized using Jamovi⁶. First, items initially formulated negatively to avoid participants' acquiescence in their answers were appropriately reversed. Then, for each scale, we computed the descriptive statistics and internal consistency using Chronbach's α (Tab. 1). All the scales with $\alpha > 0.6$ were considered consistent [3]. In our sample, female teachers were prevalent: thirty-three out of forty participants declared to be female (82.5%). The sample thus reflects the national average in Italy; according to the Italian Ministry of Education, 83.2% of teachers in public education are female [18]. Since the male population in this study is not adequately represented, no observations about gender are reported. Relating to RQ1, we conducted within-subject analyses (Wilcoxon signed-rank tests) to confront the answers between the two questionnaires.

In an effort to answer RQ2, we ran Spearman's correlation tests to verify whether teachers' age, their confidence in school technology, and educational robotics are correlated with Intention of Use, Perceived Enjoyment, Performance Expectation, and Effort Expectations. We then checked for possible differences between teachers of STEM disciplines and literary ones running independent sample T-tests. Mann-Whitney tests were carried out to look for possible differences based on teachers' type of school (kindergarten, primary, secondary).

With regard to RQ3, we ran a post-analysis on data of Public Image, Ease of

⁶ <https://www.jamovi.org/>

Usage, and Class Enjoyment scales, which were solely evaluated in Q2. We conducted Wilcoxon rank tests against the neutral scale mid-point (3 "Neither agree nor disagree", on a 5-point Likert scale).

5 Results

In connection with RQ1, we found that, with respect to Q1, answers to Q2 show a significant decrement on the majority of the scales: Agency ($p < .001$), Patency ($p = 0.005$), Mind Attribution ($p < .001$), Competence ($p < .001$), Warmth ($p = 0.012$), Intention of Use ($p < .001$), Perceived Enjoyment ($p = 0.001$), Performance Expectation ($p < .001$), and Trust ($p < .001$). No significant differences between Q1 and Q2 were evidenced for the Human-likeness ($p = 0.514$), the Likeability ($p = 0.955$), and the Effort Expectation ($p = 0.200$) scales.

Concerning the second research question, results reveal that teachers' confidence in Educational Robotics and School Technology correlates positively with Effort Expectancy (Q1): respectively $\rho = 0.378, p = 0.016$; $\rho = 0.429, p = 0.006$. In Q2, confidence in Educational Robotics showed again positive link with Effort Expectancy ($\rho = 0.387, p = 0.014$), as well as with Ease of Usage ($\rho = 0.571, p < .001$).

A significant correlation concerning Age with Agency was observed in Q1 ($\rho = -0.315, p = 0.037$). Age is also positively correlated with the Performance Expectancy expressed in Q2 ($\rho = 0.354, p = 0.025$). No significant correlation of Age with Intention of Use was found in Q1 ($\rho = 0.212, p = 0.189$), while it was present in Q2 ($\rho = 0.507, p < 0.001$). Moreover, Intention of Use presents significant positive correlations with Performance Expectations ($\rho = 0.564, p < .001$) and Perceived Enjoyment ($\rho = 0.371, p = 0.018$) in Q1.

We then checked for possible differences between teachers of STEM disciplines ($n_1 = 22$) and literary ones ($n_2 = 17$). For Q1, it was observed a difference between the two groups regarding robot's Competence, evaluated significantly higher by STEM teachers ($M_1 = 3.03, M_2 = 2.34; p = 0.047$). In Q2, after the training program, no significant difference regarding Competence was detected ($M_1 = 2.15, M_2 = 1.87; p = 0.420$). Analyses regarding teachers working in different schools (i.e., kindergarten, primary or secondary) did not evidence significant differences between these groups.

Relating to RQ3, we found that levels of all the scales significantly differ from the neutral value. In particular, Public Image ($M = 2.52, SD = 0.85; p < .001$) and Ease of Usage ($M = 2.73, SD = 0.80; p = 0.015$) levels resulted significantly lower mid-point; conversely teachers' opinion on Class Enjoyment resulted significantly positive ($M = 3.48, SD = 0.98; p = 0.995$).

6 Discussion and Conclusion

In this work, we have tried to study how a training program on robotics may affect teachers' expectations and impressions of the robot. After the training

Table 1: Descriptive statistics and internal consistencies of data from questionnaires Q1 (M_1, SD_1, α_1) and Q2 (M_2, SD_2, α_2) are reported.

Scale (1-to-5-point Likert)	M_1	SD_1	α_1	M_2	SD_2	α_2
Agency (i.e. capacity of acting, doing)	2.70	1.01	.81	2.04	0.81	.75
Patience (i.e. capacity of feeling)	1.64	0.81	.90	1.27	0.59	.94
Mind attribution (i.e. having a mind)	2.64	0.97	.86	1.88	0.85	.81
Competence (i.e. being competent, intelligent)	2.77	1.09	.81	2.04	1.03	.85
Warmth (i.e. being heartfelt, sympathetic)	2.80	1.42	.91	2.33	1.18	.84
Human-like Appearance	2.76	0.74	.73	2.66	0.69	.64
Likeability (i.e. degree of liking of the robot)	4.18	0.84	.85	4.19	0.95	.93
Intention of Use	4.01	0.80	.90	3.36	1.11	.89
Perceived Enjoyment (in using the robot)	4.24	0.57	.68	3.82	0.77	.80
Performance Expectation	3.83	0.80	.84	3.38	0.89	.90
Effort Expectation	2.44	0.91	.95	2.21	0.95	.83
Trust	2.49	1.20	.86	1.73	0.91	.71
Perceived Sociability*	-	-	-	2.56	0.97	.59
Public Image* (i.e. for using the robot at school)	-	-	-	2.52	0.85	.76
Ease of Usage*	-	-	-	2.73	0.80	.77
Class Enjoyment* (in using the robot)	-	-	-	3.48	0.98	.83

* Scales present in Q2 only.

program, participants decreased their levels of expectancy about the robot’s capabilities and autonomous skills (RQ1). This suggests that educating participants on how to use a robot results in a more realistic comprehension of the potential of the robot itself. Also, the Perceived Enjoyment of the robot lowered; this could be due to the novelty effect [15]: humans tend to be more curious and engage more with a new person, artificial agent, or object the first times they see it; then, after a few interactions, they start losing interest. This phenomenon is a well-known problem of HRI [11]. Conversely, teachers did not change their minds about the robot’s human-like appearance or about how much they liked it. Probably in evaluating these constructs, they are more influenced by the appearance of the robot and not by the interaction with it.

Furthermore, results show that the background of participants influences to a different extent, some aspects of the perception of NAO (RQ2). Specifically, our results suggest that the more teachers are confident with robotics, the more they are aware of the effort needed to interact with it. Additionally, a difference in the perception of NAO according to the subject taught by the participants is evidenced. STEM teachers tend to believe the robot is more competent compared to literature teachers, but this difference only occurs in the first moment. This could imply that the training program may have a role in leveling the robot’s

perception regardless of their teaching domain. The age of participants seems to have an impact on the evaluation of the agency of the robot and performance expectancy. This result is consistent with previous findings in the literature. As evidenced by [4] the advancement of technology may be considered new and unfamiliar to older users. Such unfamiliarity might be a concern because some researchers found that older users showed little interest and motivation in learning novel technologies ([10]. However, research also suggests that consumers starting with higher technology discomfort show a positive level of enthusiasm about their user experience in the end.

Outcomes of questionnaire Q2 show that teachers' evaluated the experience with NAO as positive for their classes (RQ3). The mean value is above the mean point of the scale (corresponding to a neutral judgment) but not to a great extent ($M = 3.48, SD = 0.98$). As reported by [3], usually, when participants are not sure how to respond, they tend to settle their responses on the mid-point of the scale. Furthermore, participants' difficulty in using the robots might have influenced their opinion in evaluating their students. Future works should put students' observations together with the ones from the teachers for a more comprehensive overview. Moreover, participants reported low levels of perceived Ease of Usage of the robot: this is in line with previous studies' observations. Teachers reported low levels also in the Public Image scale, which refers to a possible improvement of their reputation at school thanks to the use of NAO. This could be a sign that employing a robot at school is not considered prestigious: maybe, more incentives should be given to teachers to employ robots at school in order to improve their motivation and promote innovative ways of learning.

In light of the above-discussed results, we believe the present work makes some noteworthy contributions to the existing literature. We think that a course such as the one described in this study not only provides teachers with new skills but also gives them a more accurate view of the current possibilities and limits of educational robotics. This could be meaningful because it might allow teachers to become active and aware actors in robotics education. Besides, they would be able to adapt teaching methods often rigidly delivered by researchers to convey concepts to students appropriately.

In the future, it would be necessary to run more studies to gain a wider overview of teachers' impressions of educational robots also comparing to the students' ones. For example, as some works suggest that cultural background influences humans' perception of robots [13], [14], it may be interesting running a cross-cultural study involving teachers from different countries to investigate whether this effect applies to educational robotics.

Acknowledgements The "NaoToKnow" project was funded under the PNSD national call for proposals "STEAM Methodologies" and implemented by the national network of school Institutes "ARETE+4NAO, of which the Istituto Comprensivo "Goffredo Mameli" of Palestrina (RM) directed by DS Professor Ester Corsi is the leader, involving twenty-three Comprehensive Institutes in the Italian regions of Lazio, Abruzzo, Campania, Sardinia, Lombardy, Piedmont

and Emilia-Romagna. The authors wish to thank Scuola di Robotica for the support, with particular reference to Filippo Bogliolo, Gianluca Pedemonte and Emanuele Micheli. A special thank to Dr. Joshua Zonca for the support in the statistical analysis.

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